

A Review in Capabilities and Challenges of 5-Axis CNC Milling Machine Tool Operations

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Abstract:

To produce sophisticated parts with free form surfaces such as turbine blades, airfoils, impellers and aircraft components, 5-axis CNC machine tools are used. Cutting Toolpath and cutter orientation in 5-axis CNC machine tool operations are analyzed and optimized to improve performance and quality of produced parts. Sculptured surface cutting operations utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools are analyzed and modified to increase quality of part production. Cutting forces prediction and analysis are presented to provide ability of cutting force and cutting tool monitoring system along machining paths. To create and analyze actual machined parts in virtual environments, virtual machining systems are developed. Machining operations of flexible thin-walled parts using 5-axis CNC machine tools are analyzed to increase dimensional accuracy of produced parts. Tool wear prediction in 5-axis milling operations is presented to analyze and modify performance of cutting tools in milling operations. To decrease cutting tool failure in milling operations, cutting tool temperature estimation is proposed. Rotary axis of 5-axis CNC machine tools are analyzed and modified to increase precision of rotary axis during machining operations of free form surface. To increase quality of machined surfaces using 5-axis CNC machine tools, advanced machining strategies for smooth cutting tool paths are developed. Optimized cutting tool paths for minimum energy consumption are studied in order to minimize energy consumption in machining operations. Capabilities and challenges of 5-axis CNC machine tool operations is reviewed in the study in order to develop the process of part production. Thus, innovative concepts and approaches of research works in developing 5-axis CNC machine tool operations can be presented to enhance accuracy as well as efficiency in process of part manufacturing.

Keywords: 5-axis CNC machine tools, Geometrical errors, Cutting forces, Cutting tool path optimization, Accuracy of machined parts

1- Introduction

A 5-axis CNC milling machine tool is a sophisticated piece of equipment used for precision machining of complex parts with high accuracy and consistency. It has five axes of motion that can move the cutting tool in various directions to create intricate shapes and contours. The machine is designed to perform a wide range of operations, including milling, drilling, cutting, and engraving, using multiple axes of movement. A 5-axis CNC milling machine

tool can create highly complex geometries using five axes of motion during machining operations that which can be difficult or impossible to be implemented by using traditional 3-axis machine. This makes it ideal for producing parts for industries such as aerospace, medical, and automotive, where precision and complexity are critical. To obtain the maximum freedom in the orientation of the machining pathways generated by a milling cutter, 5 degree of freedom are the minimum of moved axis for the CNC machine tools [1]. Unlike traditional 3-axis machines, which can move the tool along the X, Y, and Z axes, a 5-axis machine can also tilt the tool head and rotate the workpiece. [2]. As a result, cutting tool and workpiece are relatively moving under any angle in order to create complex parts with free form surfaces.

The capabilities of 5-axis CNC machine tools can be presented as,

1. High precision: A 5-axis CNC milling machine tool is capable of producing highly precise parts with tight tolerances, as it can move the cutting tool in five different directions, allowing for greater control over the machining process.
2. Complex shapes: The machine can produce complex shapes and contours that would be difficult or impossible to achieve with traditional machining methods, such as 3-axis milling machines.
3. Increased efficiency: The 5-axis CNC milling machine tool can perform multiple operations in a single setup, reducing the need for manual intervention and increasing efficiency.
4. Reduced setup time: The machine's ability to perform multiple operations in a single setup also reduces the setup time required for each operation, which can lead to faster production times and increased productivity.
5. Reduced scrap: With the ability to machine parts from multiple angles, 5-axis CNC milling machines can reduce the amount of material wasted during manufacturing, resulting in less scrap and lower costs.
6. Improved surface finish: The ability to rotate and tilt the tool in multiple directions allows 5-axis CNC milling machines to produce parts with smooth and uniform surfaces.
7. Versatility: The 5-axis CNC milling machine tool is capable of producing a broad variety of parts and components for a number of different sectors, including aerospace, automotive, medical, and electronics.

The challenges of 5-axis CNC machine tools can be presented as,

1. Cost: 5-axis CNC milling machines are typically more expensive than traditional 3-axis machines, which can be a barrier to entry for smaller businesses.
2. Complex programming: 5-axis CNC milling machines require advanced programming skills to set up and operate, which can be a challenge for operators who are not experienced with this technology.
3. Skill requirements: The operation of a 5-axis CNC milling machine tool requires specialized knowledge and expertise, which can be challenging to acquire and retain.
4. Maintenance: The machine requires regular maintenance and calibration to ensure accurate and reliable operation, which can be time-consuming and costly. With more moving parts and axes, 5-axis CNC milling machines require more maintenance than traditional 3-axis machines, which can add to the cost and complexity of operating and maintaining these machines.
5. Tooling: The machine requires specialized tooling, which can be expensive and may require additional setup time.
6. Safety: 5-axis CNC milling machines require additional safety measures, including guarding and safety interlocks, to prevent operator injury.

Axis configuration of 5-axis CNC machine tool is presented in figure 1 [3].

Fig. 1. Axis configuration of 5-axis CNC machine tool where a machine with orientable-spindle (left) and a machine with orientable-table (right) [3].

Part manufacturing operations are essential for the production of a wide range of products, from consumer goods to industrial machinery. They enable the creation of high-quality, reliable, and cost-effective products that meet the needs of businesses and consumers alike. Without part manufacturing operations, it would not be possible to produce the various components that make up a product, such as machine parts, electronic components, and structural materials.

5-axis CNC milling machines are sophisticated machines that offer several advantages over traditional 3-axis machines. They are used in a variety of industries to machine complex parts with high precision and accuracy. The programming, tooling, and machining strategies for 5-axis CNC milling machines are different from those used for 3-axis machines and require specialized knowledge and expertise. So, the accuracy as well as productivity in process of part production using five-axis CNC milling machines are studied in different research works.

To enhance accuracy and efficiency in process of part production utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools, different topics and issues of research works are considered and presented. Errors of machine tool structures as well as machining operation errors are analyzed to improve precision of machined parts [4]. To improve the effectiveness and quality of component manufacture utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools, cutting tool trajectories along machining processes of free form surfaces are evaluated and adjusted. To increase accuracy of the axis in machining operations of free form surfaces, rotary axis of 5-axis CNC machine tools are analyzed and modified. Cutting forces are anticipated and assessed in order to keep track of the state of the cutting tool as well as the tool deflection inaccuracy [5]. Virtual machining systems are developed in order to produce and evaluate the real machined components in virtual environments [6]. To increase safety in cutting operations of free form surfaces, collision detection systems are introduced. Feed rate scheduling and optimization systems in 5-axis CNC machine tool operations are created to increase surface quality in machined parts. To minimize the energy consumption in the machining operation, optimized cutting tool paths can be generated [7]. Also, Intelligent Computer Aided Process Planning (CAPP) solutions are introduced to enhance decision-making and knowledge management during the component manufacturing process. To enhance accuracy in five-axis milling operations of turbine blades, application of virtual machining system in deformation error compensation is proposed by Soori [8].

In order to enhance the machined surfaces precision through 5 Axis CNC end milling, geometrical error modelling and compensation methodologies are presented [9, 10]. Advanced compensation methodology such as actual inverse kinematic model based on the measured errors of the different axis of CNC machine tools are proposed in order to eliminate the error effects to the machined components [11]. Advanced error metrology systems are discussed in order to measure and simulate the machining operations error in terms of accuracy enhancement of machining operations [12, 13]. Different devices such as single ballbar set-up [14] and indigenous temperature sensors [15] are used in order to provide error mapping matrix in terms of enhancing the accuracy of 5 axis CNC milling machine tools [16]. To increase surface quality in machined parts, machining operations of sculptured surfaces using five axis CNC machine tools are presented [17, 18]. Time-optimal tool motion planning [19] and geometrical model of the part surfaces [20] are studied in order to improve the precision of manufactured part

surfaces. To increase the tool-path feed and to obtain an optimized feedrate profile, advanced feed rate scheduling and optimization system is proposed. So, the tool axis orientation tracking errors and machining times can be minimized by using the proposed method of feed scheduling [21, 22]. To evaluate the machining processes using five axis CNC machine tools, developed models of cutting force calculation is studied [23]. As a result, the errors due to the cutting forces such as tool deflection error can be accurately predicted in order to be compensated [24]. To reduce the changing of tool orientation during machining operations and enhance the quality of surface roughness, advanced cutting tool paths optimization systems are created [22]. So, the five axis machining processes' kinematic characteristics can be improved [25]. To examine and adjust machining procedures as well as machined components. in digital environments, advanced virtual machining systems are developed [26]. Moreover, the different errors as well as challenges of the five axis CNC machining can be simulated in digital environments in order to be minimized [27]. To increase the precision of manufactured parts, accuracy analysis and enhancement of rotary axis of the five axis CNC machine tools are discussed [28]. To improve precision and efficiency in flexible thin-walled components 5-axis flank end milling, advanced methods of thin walled parts machining operations is investigated [29, 30]. The cutting tool paths can also be developed by modification of tool tip position and tool axis orientation in order to minimize the deflection error during five-axis flank milling of thin-walled parts [31]. Tool wear estimation is studied in order to predict and modify the tool wear conditions and decrease the cutting tool failure during free form surfaces 5 axis milling operations [32]. To enhance the surface quality and cutting tool life in machined parts, cutting tool temperature during five axis machining operations are investigated [33]. Also, adaptive self-learning compensation approach can be applied to the thermal errors in order to compensate the thermal errors during 5 axis milling operations [34]. Flank milling as well as sweep milling operations using five axis CNC machine tools is studied in order to enhance precision as well as surface quality in the machined parts [35]. Gouging error detection and elimination methods is presented to improve machined parts precision. As a result, tool orientation optimization method in terms gouge-free tool axis movements in terms of improving part production precision can be presented [36]. To increase safety in machining processes of part production using 5 Axis CNC machine tools, collision detection systems are presented [37]. Post-processor for 5-axis CNC machine tools is modified in order to compensate the tool radius error as well as geometric errors of CNC machine tools [38]. To enhance precision and efficiency in 5 axis CNC machining operations, Intelligent Computer Aided Process Planning (CAPP) systems are also discussed [39]. To increase the machined parts surface quality, advanced machining strategies for smooth cutting tool paths is investigated [40, 41]. So, the smooth cutting tool paths for machining pockets in five axes with continuous curve and an uniform cutting force can be presented to improve the precision of machined components [42]. To minimize the energy consumption in five-axis end milling operations of freeform surfaces, optimized cutting tool paths is suggested [43, 44]. As a consequence, the cost of producing parts utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools can be reduced by reducing energy consumption during the process [45]. As a result, accuracy as well as reliability of machined parts using the five-axis CNC machine tools can be enhanced in order to increase added values in process of part production.

Meta-heuristic algorithms for assessing the collapse risk of steel moment frame mid-rise buildings is presented by Karimi Ghaleh Jough and Şensoy [46] in order to provide a better risk management strategy in steel moment frames. Steel Moment-Resisting Frame Dependability via Interval Analysis using the FCM-PSO Method is studied by Karimi Ghaleh Jough and Şensoy [47] to enhance accuracy and decrease execution time in calculation of seismic fragility curves. Assessment of out-of-plane behavior of non-structural masonry walls using FE simulations is presented by Karimi Ghaleh Jough and Golhashem [48] in order to reduce self-weight axial compression of the walls with modern lightweight masonry units. Uncertainty analysis through development of seismic fragility curve for an SMRF structure using an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system based on fuzzy C-means algorithm is implemented by Karimi Ghaleh Jough and Beheshti Aval [49] to incorporate epistemic uncertainty and increasing calculation accuracy. Road map to BIM use for infrastructure domains: Identifying and contextualizing variables of infrastructure projects is presented by Ghasemzadeh et al. [50] to identify and prove the existing lack of using BIM for infrastructure projects. Epistemic Uncertainty Treatment Using Group Method of Data Handling Algorithm in Seismic Collapse Fragility is presented by Karimi Ghaleh Jough et al. [51] to increase accuracy and precision of the outputs as well as power with the same computational time compared to aforementioned methods. Uncertainty Interval Analysis of Steel Moment Frame by

Development of 3D-Fragility Curves Towards Optimized Fuzzy Method is presented by Karimi Ghaleh Jough and Ghasemzadeh [52] to enhance accuracy and reduce execution time in driving the 3D-fragility curves. The contribution of steel wallposts to out-of-plane behavior of non-structural masonry walls is investigated by Karimi Ghaleh Jough [53] to provide smaller modification factors in masonry walls with wallpost. To decrease the environmental pollution during manufacturing process, sustainable CNC machining operations is studied by Soori et al. [54]. To enhance the performances of steel moment structures during working conditions, applications of artificial intelligent in optimization of steel moment frame structures is reviewed by Soori and Karimi Ghaleh Jough [55]. Reliability prediction of SMRF based on the combination of neural network and incremental dynamic analysis is implemented by Karimi Ghaleh Jough and Ghasemzadeh in order to enhance performances by decreasing random uncertainty in steel structures [56]. To enhance productivity in industry 4.0, applications of smart robotics systems is reviewed by Soori et al. [57]. Prediction of seismic collapse risk in steel moment framed structures by metaheuristic algorithm is implemented by Karimi Ghaleh Jough [57] to enhance the performances of steel moment framed structures.

Soori et al. [58-62] proposed virtual machining methods for improving and assessing CNC machining in virtual settings. Soori et al. [63] provided an overview of recent advancements in friction stir welding techniques in order to analyze and improve performance in the component production process using welding processes. Soori and Asmael [64] investigated the use of virtual machining technology to reduce residual stress and displacement inaccuracy during five-axis milling operations for turbine blades. Soori and Asmael [65] investigated possibilities of virtualized machining methods to monitor and lower the cutting temperature while milling things that are challenging to cut. Soori et al. [66] suggested the implementation of a sophisticated virtual machining technique to enhance surface properties during turbine blade five-axis milling operations. Soori and Asmael [67] developed virtual milling procedures to lower dislocation error in impeller blade five-axis milling operations. Soori [68] presented virtual invention as an attempt to examine and improve the part production process in virtual settings.

Soori and Asmael [69] Presented a summary of recent developments from literature to evaluate and improve the parameter approach for machining process optimization. To enhance energy consumption efficiency, data availability and quality throughout the supply chain, and component manufacturing precision and reliability, Dastres et al. [70] proposed a review of RFID-based wireless manufacturing systems. Soori et al. [71] investigated the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning to CNC machine tools in order to increase efficiency and profitability in component production processes. In order to enhance the functionality of machined parts, Soori and Arezoo [72] examined the subject of residual stress measurement and reduction in machining operations. To enhance the integrity of the surface and reduce residual stress while grinding Inconel 718, Soori and Arezoo [73] recommended employing the Taguchi optimization approach to determine the ideal machining settings. To prolong the life of the cutters used in machining processes, Soori and Arezoo [74] investigated various approaches for tool wear prediction algorithms. Soori and Asmael [75] examined the use of computer-assisted process planning to increase component manufacturing method efficiency. Dastres and Soori [76] examined how to utilize advancements in web-based decision support systems to provide solutions for data warehouse administration through support for decision-making. Dastres and Soori [77] examined uses of artificial neural networks to investigate methods to implement them to increase the efficacy of products. Dastres and Soori [78] suggested using communication systems in environmental issues to reduce the detrimental impacts of technology development on natural disasters. To improve the internet security of networks and data, Dastres and Soori [79] suggested the secure socket layer.

Dastres and Soori [80] evaluated and suggested the gaps between suggested ways in order to create the decision support systems methodology by studying the advancements in web-based decision support systems. To improve network security protocols, Dastres and Soori [81] provided a review of the most current developments in network threats. To expand image processing systems' potential for a variety of purposes, Dastres and Soori [82] examined systems for image processing and analysis. Dimensional, geometrical, tool deflection, and thermal defects have been modified by Soori and Arezoo [83] to improve accuracy in 5-axis CNC milling processes. Recent developments in published articles are examined by Soori et al. [84] in order to evaluate and enhance deep learning, machine learning, and artificial intelligence's effects on advanced robots. Soori and Arezoo [85] created a virtual machining system application to investigate if the tool life and cutting temperature throughout milling operations are influenced by the cutting parameters. Soori and Arezoo [86] investigated how coolant affected the cutting temperature, surface

roughness, and tool wear when turning Ti6Al4V alloy. A review of recent advances from published publications is conducted by Soori[87] in order to investigate and modify composite constructions and materials. Soori et al. [88] studied how to improve quality control and streamline part production operations in industry 4.0 smart factories by utilizing the Internet of Things. To reduce the amount of wear on cutting tools while drilling, Soori and Arezoo [89] proposed a virtual machining system. Soori and Arezoo [90] reduced surface roughness and residual stress to raise the overall quality of products made with abrasive water jet cutting. In order to improve the precision of five-axis milling operations for turbine blades, Soori [8] calculates and compensates for deformation errors. Soori and Arezoo [91] studied the application of the finite element approach in CNC machine tool modification in order to assess and improve accuracy in CNC machining processes and components. Soori et al. [92] studied several energy use optimization techniques in order to assess and optimize energy consumption in industrial robots. Soori et al. [93] examined the negative and positive aspects of virtual manufacturing systems in order to assess and improve the part production process in Industry 4.0. In order to develop the supply chain management in advanced manufacturing, artificial neural networks are studied by Soori et al. [94]. battery state estimation strategies using machine learning for battery management systems of aircraft propulsion batteries is reviewed by Raoofi and Yildiz [95] in order to enhance the battery management of future electric aircrafts. Analysis of frontier digital technologies in continuing airworthiness management frameworks and applications is studied by Raoofi and Yasar [96] in order to elaborate on the existing link between maintenance practices and the digital world while also highlighting any unaddressed potential for digital transformation in aircraft maintenance.

A review of recent development of 5 axis CNC milling machine tools operations is proposed in the study to investigate the recent development in the part production process using 5 axis CNC milling machine tools. Different errors measuring and compensation methodologies, different machining strategies and cutting tool path optimization, cutting forces prediction methods, cutting tool parameter optimization methods, virtual machining systems, advanced computer aided process planning systems, machining operations of flexible thin walled parts with free form surfaces and minimization of energy consumption methods in different published papers are reviewed in this paper which created a novel review paper in capabilities and challenges of 5-axis CNC milling machine tools.

One of the significant contributions of research in analysis and modification of 5-axis CNC machine tools is the development of advanced software and hardware that enable 5-axis CNC milling machines to perform complex machining operations with high precision and accuracy. For instance, researchers have developed algorithms that improve the tool path planning process and reduce machining time, thus increasing productivity. The study can also develop software that enables the creation of 3D models of parts, which can be used to simulate machining operations and optimize machining parameters. It will also led to the development of new machining strategies during machining operations of free form surfaces. These strategies are designed to overcome some of the inherent limitations of 5-axis CNC milling machines, such as tool deflection and part accessibility. For example, researchers have developed adaptive machining strategies that adjust the cutting parameters in real-time to compensate the tool deflection. They have also developed new tool geometries and tool holders that improve part accessibility, thus enabling the machining of complex geometries.

The research work in the field has a crucial role in enhancing accuracy and productivity in various industries. The development of advanced software and hardware, new machining strategies, and new materials and surface coatings have enabled 5-axis CNC milling machines to perform complex machining operations with high precision and accuracy, thus improving productivity and reducing manufacturing costs. Therefore, it believes that by examining and analyzing current successes from published papers, concepts can be proposed to enhance the CNC milling machining processes.

Geometric error modelling and compensation in 5-axis CNC machine tools is presented in Section 2. The section 3 discusses the errors metrology systems in 5-axis CNC machine tool. 5-axis CNC machining operations of sculptured surfaces is presented in section 4. Feed rate scheduling and optimization systems and cutting forces prediction in 5-axis CNC machining operations are presented in section 5 and 6 respectively. The section 7 discusses the optimization of cutting toolpaths in 5-axis CNC machining operations. Virtual machining system is presented in section 8. Accuracy analysis and enhancement of rotary axis in 5-axis CNC machine tools is presented in section 9. Machining operations of flexible thin-walled parts and tool wear prediction in 5 Axis milling operations are presented in sections 10 and 11 respectively. Cutting tool temperatures estimation is presented in section 12. The section 13 presents flank milling operations in 5-axis CNC machine tools. Sweep milling in 5-axis milling operations and gouging error detection and

elimination methods are presented in sections 14 and 15 respectively. Collision detection systems in 5-axis CNC machining operations is discussed in section 16. Development of post-processor in 5-axis CNC machine tools is presented in section 17. Intelligent Computer Aided Process Planning (CAPP) systems and advanced machining strategies for smooth cutting tool paths are presented in sections 18 and 19 respectively. Cutting tool paths Optimization for minimum energy consumption is presented in section 20. Finally, conclusion and future research work directions are presented in section 21.

2- Geometric error modelling and compensation in 5-axis CNC machine tools

A new approach of compensation for geometrical errors of five-axis machine tools is proposed to increase the precision of positioning during milling [97]. The cutting tool orientation error compensation methodology based on motion of linear and rotation axis of CNC machine tools is proposed in the study in order to precisely compensate the geometry errors in five axis CNC milling operations. A Compensation methodology for systematic errors in 5-axis NC machining is modified to enhance precision in produced parts using the 5-axis CNC machine tools [98]. Also, to obtain the volumetric error due to geometric error in the machining operations of 5-axis CNC machine tools, a new mathematical methodology is modified [99]. So, the errors can be measured and compensated in order to enhance precision in process of part production using CNC machining operations. To create faster tool path and a better surface quality in produced parts, a new methodology in cutting tool path computation for the geometrical errors in 5-axis CNC machine tools operations using B-Spline curves is modified [100]. Real-time error correction for improvement of five-axis CNC machines' accuracy is modified to boost position accuracy across the board for five-axis CNC machine tool operation [101]. To improve the efficiency and method of designing five-axis postprocessors, the creation of a generic five-axis postprocessor based on a machine tool's generalized kinematics modelling is described [102]. NURBS-based quick geometric error correction for 5 axis CNC machine machines is modified to increase accuracy and productivity during producing parts [103]. In order to enhance the component production precision utilizing volumetric error compensation, the accurate detection and compensation of geometric errors of 5-axis CNC machine tools using double ball bar is proposed [104]. The tool tip and workpiece dimensions and geometric errors in 5-Axis CNC machine tool processes can be described by the kinematic chain of machine axes. The homogeneous transformation matrices are utilized in the error analysis software may to model the dimensions and geometrical errors of the five axis CNC machine tools. Figure 2 depicts the 5-axis machine tool's structure and kinematic chain [104].

Fig. 2. The 5-axis machine tool's setup and kinematic chain [104].

Each Homogeneous transformation matrices is therefore defined mathematically for each machine axis as follows [8]:

$${}^i T_j = {}^i T_j^L \cdot T_j^M \quad (1)$$

Where ${}^i T_j$ is an homogeneous transformation matrices to describe the actual position and orientation of the coordinate system j with respect to the coordinate system i, and ${}^i T_j^L$ as well as T_j^M presents the location and motion relationship between coordinate system i and j respectively. So, the location of each point on the workpiece table can be introduced by using the kinematic chain as shown in the figure 2. By considering the reference coordinate system for the workpiece table, the kinematic equation can be described as [104]:

$$[P_w \ 1] = {}^r T_w [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 1]^T \quad (2)$$

$${}^r T_w = {}^r T_y \cdot {}^y T_x \cdot {}^x T_a \cdot {}^a T_c \cdot {}^c T_w \quad (3)$$

Where the ${}^c T_w$ is the location of the point on the workpiece table which can be presented as [104]:

$${}^c T_w = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & X_{wp} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & Y_{wp} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & Z_{wp} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \delta_{xw} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \delta_{yw} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \delta_{zw} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Where, X_{wp} , Y_{wp} and Z_{wp} are the x, y and z componets of the error location of P_w regarding to the X_c , Y_c and Z_c as well as the δ_{xw} , δ_{yw} and δ_{zw} .

Each dimensional error of the moving axis can be described by using the matrices of homogeneous transformation presented in the Eq. (4) in order to be used in the virtual machining system.

3- Errors metrology systems in 5-axis CNC machine tool

Metrology systems are essential for assuring the correctness and precision of 5-axis CNC machine tools. However, errors can still occur in these systems, which can impact the quality and reliability of the machined parts [105]. Some common errors in metrology systems in 5-axis CNC machine tools include:

1. Positioning errors: These errors occur when the machine tool fails to achieve the desired position accurately. This can be caused by factors such as mechanical wear and tear, temperature fluctuations, and vibrations [106].
2. Geometric errors: These errors occur when the machine tool deviates from the ideal geometric shape, leading to inaccuracies in the machined parts. This can be caused by factors such as misalignment of the axes, deformation of the machine structure, and tool deflection.
3. Calibration errors: These errors occur when the metrology system is not calibrated properly. This can lead to inaccuracies in the measurements, which can impact the precision and accuracy of the machine tool [107].
4. Software errors: These errors occur when there are bugs or glitches in the software used to control the metrology system. This can lead to incorrect measurements and inaccurate machine tool movements.

In order to enhance precision throughout the component manufacturing process using 5-axis milling machine with two rotating axes, the R-Test analysis techniques for error calibration of rotary axis is proposed [108]. Dynamic precision evaluation for five-axis machine tools utilizing S trajectory divergence dependent on R-test measurement is studied to find and compensate machining errors in 5-axis CNC machine tools [109]. To enhance precision of 5-axis CNC machine tools, application of Renishaw ball-bar system for measuring and compensating the errors of CNC machine tool element is proposed [110]. In order to improve precision in machine parts using five-axis CNC machine tools, monitoring orientation, static and circularity errors of a CNC Vertical Machining Center for confirming the machining is studied [111]. Geometrical error modelling and characterization on 5-axis machine tool is investigated to develop the machining operations using 5 axis CNC machine tools [112]. In order to reduce inaccuracies in the Ballbar testing of the rotary axes in 5-axis machines, a new approach for discovering location problems in 5-axis machine tools utilizing a single ballbar setup is examined [14].

To improve the precision in machine components using five-axis machine tools, a technique for systematic geometrical error correction in cutting tool paths of free from surface is suggested [113]. An innovative method to distinguish geometric inaccuracy of the rotary axis of multi-axis machine tool is proposed in order to offer high-efficiency and high-precision measurement technology in process of five axis CNC machining operations [114]. Moreover, an advanced coordinate calibration system for five-axis machine tool is proposed in order to improve the error measuring systems in CNC machining operations [115].

To minimize calibration errors, errors, thermal errors, Software errors, Electrical noise and vibration during 5-axis CNC machining operations, it is important to use high-quality metrology equipment, follow proper calibration procedures, regularly maintain the machine tool and its sensors, and use software that is well-tested and up-to-date. Additionally, monitoring the performance of the metrology systems over time can help identify potential issues before they become serious problems.

4- 5-axis CNC machining operations of sculptured surfaces

Sculptured surfaces can be machined using 5-axis CNC machines with various machining operations [116]. Here are some of the common machining operations used in 5-axis CNC for sculptured surfaces:

1. **Contouring:** This is a common operation used for machining complex surfaces with 5-axis CNC machines. In this operation, the tool follows a predefined path along the surface to create the desired shape. The tool is usually a ball-nose end mill, which is ideal for machining curved surfaces.
2. **Swarf cutting:** Swarf cutting is another milling technique which 5-axis CNC machines can utilize to produce sculptured surfaces. In this operation, the tool is tilted to the surface to be machined, and a continuous tool path is created along the surface to remove material. This operation is typically used for roughing operations [117].
3. **Surface finishing:** Surface finishing is a final operation used to achieve a smooth surface finish on sculptured surfaces. In this operation, a finishing tool is used to machine the surface with a high level of precision and control. This operation is commonly used in the aerospace and automotive industries for producing high-quality surface finishes [118].
4. **Parallel finishing:** Parallel finishing is another operation that can be used for machining sculptured surfaces. In this operation, the tool is tilted at a certain angle to the surface and moves along the surface in a series of parallel passes. This operation is typically used for finishing operations.
5. **Z-level finishing:** Z-level finishing is a machining operation used to create a series of horizontal planes on the surface of the workpiece. This operation is typically used for roughing operations and can be used to create a flat surface on a curved or irregular surface.
6. **Inspection:** Once the machining is complete, the part is inspected using precision measuring instruments to ensure that it meets the required tolerances and surface finish.

To simulate material removal throughout milling operations on sculptured surfaces utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools, modeling of cutting geometry and forces is modified [116]. To investigate the influence of the milling parameters on the surface finish of produced parts, sculptured surface milling procedures utilizing three and five axes is studied [119]. In order to improve surface quality of machined parts, , locally ideal cutting spots for 5-axis sculptured surface machining processes using the dupin indicatrices of the cutter surface and specified surface at the contact point is suggested [120]. To increase dimensional accuracy of the machined components, sculptured surface five-axis ball-end milling using tool deflection error compensation is discussed [24]. To increase surface quality in machined parts, adaptive method of 5-axis milling of sculptured surfaces elements with a curved line contour is suggested [121]. An accurate forecast approach of cutting forces in 5-axis flank milling of sculptured surface is proposed to reduce cutting tool loss in machining operations [122]. An advanced convex hull approach in machining of complicated sculptured surfaces is proposed in order to obtain the best multi-point 5-axis tool placement for [123]. To reduce the overall cycle time in milling operations, intelligent tool paths for 5-axis ball-end milling of curvaceous surfaces using process models is presented [22].

Overall, the sculptured surfaces machining operations in 5 axis CNC is a complex process that requires a combination of CAD/CAM software, specialized cutting tools, and precision machining equipment. However, with the proper tools and techniques, it is possible to create highly accurate and intricate shapes with a high-quality surface finish. Some potential areas of future research can be optimizing tool paths, adaptive machining strategies, integration with CAD/CAM software in order to enhance accuracy in complex and highly accurate sculptured surfaces.

5- Feed rate scheduling and optimization systems in 5-axis CNC machining operations

Feed rate scheduling and optimization systems in 5-axis CNC machines are designed to improve machining efficiency by optimizing the feed rates of the cutting tools while taking into account the machine's capabilities, the material being cut, and the desired surface finish. The goal of feed rate optimization is to maximize the material removal rate while minimizing tool wear and ensuring that the finished part meets the required specifications. This is achieved by using advanced algorithms that take into account the machine's capabilities, the tool geometry, the material properties, and the cutting conditions.

One approach to feed rate optimization is to use adaptive control systems that monitor the cutting forces in real-time and adjust the feed rate accordingly. These systems use sensors to measure the cutting forces and adjust the feed rate based on the measured values. This allows the machine to maintain a constant chip load, which improves tool life and reduces the risk of tool failure. Another approach to feed rate optimization is to use advanced software that simulates the machining process and predicts the optimal feed rate for a given material and cutting condition. These systems use complex algorithms to model the material removal process and optimize the feed rate to achieve the desired rate of material removal and surface finish. In addition to feed rate optimization, scheduling systems are used to optimize the sequence and timing of machining operations to minimize idle time and maximize machine utilization. These systems use advanced algorithms to schedule the machining operations based on the available resources, the tooling requirements, and the desired delivery date.

In order to maximize the feed along the tool-path without going beyond the planned feed and the physical constraints of the drives, feed optimization for five-axis CNC machine tools including drive boundaries is invented [124]. Feedrate extrapolation with axis jerk restrictions on 5-axis NURBS and G1 tool path is studied in order to produce an optimum feedrate profile that best utilizes the kinematical properties of the 5 axis CNC machine tool procedures [125]. An advanced five-axis CNC machine using adaptive feedrate scheduling approach of dual NURBS curve parameterization is created to predict the feed profile of linear and angular feed acceleration sensitive areas in machining operations of free form structures [126]. To provide a reliable and accurate methodology of improving machined component precision in five-axis machining operations, an enhanced feedrate scheduling approach using NURBS interpolation algorithm is provided [127]. A novel master-based feedrate scheduling algorithm is developed to provide Feedrate scheduling with consideration of kinematic and real-time constraints in five-axis machining operations [128]. Figure 3 depicts a master-based feedrate scheduling framework with kinematic restrictions for five-axis machining processes [128]. A geometry module, a kinematic module, and a feedrate scheduling module make up its three primary modules of the proposed feed rate scheduling system in the study. The geometry module takes the toolpath's geometric characteristics and extracts data. The corner feedrate and tooltip feed parameters are set by the kinematic module. The tangential feedrate profile is planned using the bidirectional scanning technique, which can create smooth feed motion in the feedrate scheduling module [128].

Fig. 3. Master-based feedrate scheduling algorithm with kinematic constraints for five-axis machining operations [128].

A new extended parameterized interpolation approach is presented by considering the machine contour inaccuracies and the reduction of feedrate variation in order to optimize the specifications of five-axis CNC machining

processes [129]. To analyze the accuracy of machined parts and optimize the toolpath in five-axis ball-end milling, tool movement analysis and optimization method is proposed [130]. To determine the optimal geometric sequence in five axis machining operations of free form surfaces, feedrate planning for parametric tool path approximation is investigated [131]. To provide an advanced feed rate scheduling systems in 5-Axis milling operations, planning and optimization of jerk-limited feedrates using a novel piecewise linear programming technique is suggested [132]. Overall, feed rate scheduling and optimization systems are essential tools for improving the efficiency and productivity of 5-axis CNC machines, while ensuring that the finished parts meet the required specifications. Machine Learning-based feed rate optimization and multiple objectives such as minimizing machining time, maximizing tool life, and achieving high surface quality can be simultaneously considered in terms of feed rate scheduling and optimization systems in 5-axis CNC machining operations.

6- Cutting forces prediction and analysis

Cutting forces prediction and analysis in 5-axis CNC (computer numerical control) machining is a complex task that requires knowledge of machining parameters, cutting tool geometry, material properties, and the machine tool's dynamic behavior [133]. However, it is critical to determine the cutting forces because excessive forces can lead to tool failure, poor surface finish, and reduced accuracy of the machined part [134].

Here are some techniques that can be used to predict and analyze cutting forces in 5-axis CNC machining:

1. Analytical models: Analytical models are based on mathematical equations that describe the cutting forces as a function of machining parameters and material properties. These models can be developed for specific machining operations and can provide a good estimate of cutting forces [135].
2. Finite Element Analysis (FEA): FEA is a numerical method used to simulate the machining process and predict cutting forces. In FEA, the workpiece, cutting tool, and machine tool are modelled as a 3D mesh, and the cutting forces are calculated using the laws of mechanics [136].
3. Experimental methods: Experimental methods involve measuring the cutting forces during machining using force sensors. These methods provide the most accurate estimate of cutting forces, but they are time-consuming and expensive [137].
4. Empirical models: Empirical models are based on experimental data and are developed using regression analysis. These algorithms can be used to evaluate cutting forces for similar machining operations [138].

To optimize machining settings and raise the caliber of the machined item, it is crucial to assess the outcomes in addition to forecasting cutting forces. For instance, using excessive cutting forces might result in tool wear and a poor surface quality, whereas using low cutting forces can lead to insufficient material removal rates and longer machining times [139]. Therefore, the cutting forces should be analyzed in conjunction with other machining parameters such as spindle speed, feed rate, and tool geometry to optimize the machining process [140].

In order to create optimized tool path and orientation during 5-axis machining, chip volume and cutting force estimations in metal cutting of free-form surfaces utilizing flat-end mills are studied [141]. Cutting force and chip volume forecasts during 5-axis CNC machining of curved surfaces utilizing flat-end machines is proposed in the study to calculate the optimized CNC tool path and the optimal feed-rate along machining paths. Chip plowing volume and force calculation in 5-axis CNC micro-milling using flat-end mills are presented in order to avoid ploughing effects in micro-milling operations [142]. To provide the ability of cutting forces monitoring along the five-axis tool paths as well as tool condition monitoring systems in virtual environments, prediction of cutting forces in 5-Axis milling operations using feed drive current measurements is suggested [143]. Cutting force predictions and chip volume for flat-end mills used in 5-axis CNC machining of free-form surfaces are investigated to perform cutting force estimation for generating optimal tool path and orientation during 5-axis milling operations [144]. To boost performance in machining operations of free form surfaces, offline control strategy and feedrate scheduling for complicated free

form surfaces in 5-axis milling is proposed [145]. During five-axis machining with ball-end cutters, the improvement of cutter orientation based on cutting force estimation is suggested [146].

7- Optimization of cutting toolpaths in 5-axis CNC machining operations

In 5-axis CNC milling, the toolpath and cutter orientation optimization systems are crucial for achieving efficient and high-quality machining [147]. Here are some key aspects of these systems:

1. Toolpath optimization: The toolpath is the path that the cutting tool follows while machining the part. The optimization of the toolpath involves finding the most efficient path for the tool to follow, taking into account factors such as the geometry of the part, the cutting tool's capabilities, and the desired surface finish. There are various toolpath strategies, such as linear, zigzag, spiral, and contour, which can be used depending on the machining requirements [148].
2. Cutter orientation optimization: The cutter orientation refers to the inclination at which the cutter is placed with respect to the part surface. The optimization of cutter orientation involves finding the optimal angle for the tool to achieve the desired surface finish and to avoid collisions with the part or the machine [149].
3. Collision avoidance: The sophisticated kinematic design of the 5-axis CNC milling machine raises the possibility of collisions between the tool and the component or the machine body. Collision avoidance systems are used to detect and avoid collisions by adjusting the toolpath or the cutter orientation in real-time.
4. Simulation and verification: Simulation and verification systems are used to visualize the machining process and to verify that the toolpath and cutter orientation are optimized for the part. This helps to avoid errors and ensure that the final part meets the desired specifications.

To minimize the changing of tool orientation during machining operations and increase the quality of surface roughness, the optimizing tool orientations during 5-axis machining using configuration-space search method is presented [150]. To improve surface roughness in free form surface machining operations, developed optimum tool orientation control for ball-end cutter 5-axis CNC milling is presented [151]. 5-axis high-speed machining is optimized using a surface-based strategy to maintain cutting conditions and surface integrity while preserving the machined part's geometrical alignment [152]. To optimize the cutting tool paths, machining Surface in 5 axes CNC milling operations are defined as the guiding surface and the orientation surface which are shown in the figure 4 [152]. The orientation surface in cutting tool pathways can then be improved, which will improve tool axis orientations.

Fig. 4. Specification of the Milling Surface for CNC operations utilizing five axes CNC machine [152].

To increase material removal rate and enhance surface properties of machined components, chatter-free tool orientations for 5-axis ball-end milling is established [153]. Optimal 5-axis flank CNC machining of free-form surfaces is achieved by adjusting the envelopes of the surfaces of rotation is created in order to achieve the optimal cutting tool routes in 5-axis CNC machining operations [154]. The process of toolpath generation and material removal simulation algorithms for the blisk model is shown in the figure 5 [154].

Fig. 5. The algorithms for creating toolpaths and simulating material removal for the blisk model. The green color represents the machined patch under examination. (b, c). The milling tool carrying device is represented by a blue cone. (d) [154].

Adaptive curvilinear toolpaths for five-axis machining of STL surfaces is provided to reduce the length and machining time of the cutting toolpath [155]. To increase the machining productivity of sculptured surface machining, a machining potential field technique to tool path generation for multi-axis sculptured surface machining is proposed [156]. Overall, the toolpath and cutter orientation optimization systems are critical for achieving efficient and high-quality 5-axis CNC milling. They require a combination of advanced algorithms, software, and hardware to ensure that the machining process is safe, accurate, and efficient.

8- Virtual machining systems

Virtual machining systems (VMS) are software tools that allow CNC machinists and engineers to simulate the machining process in a virtual environment. With VMS, users can create a digital model of the part they want to machine, select the tooling and cutting parameters, and then simulate the cutting process to optimize the machining strategy before actually running the job on a physical machine. Virtual machining systems can help to overcome these challenges by allowing the user to simulate the machining process in a virtual environment. The user can input the tool path, cutting parameters, and other variables into the system, and the system will simulate the cutting process in real time, allowing the user to see how the material is being removed and how the tool is interacting with the workpiece. In the case of 5-axis CNC machining, VMS are particularly useful because they allow users to visualize and optimize complex cutting paths and tool orientations that would be difficult to program manually. Some of the key features of VMS for 5-axis CNC machining include:

1. Collision detection: VMS can simulate the cutting process and check for potential collisions between the cutting tool and the part, the tool and the machine, or the part and the machine. This helps users avoid costly mistakes and optimize the tool path.
2. Toolpath optimization: VMS can suggest optimized tool paths based on the part geometry and the selected cutting parameters, taking into account factors such as tool reach, orientation, and tool changes.
3. Real-time feedback: VMS can provide real-time feedback on the machining process, allowing users to monitor cutting forces, tool wear, and other critical parameters.
4. Post-processing: VMS can generate G-code programs for 5-axis CNC machines, including tool path data and cutting parameters, based on the simulation results.

To examine and optimize machine tool components using finite element models, an advanced virtual machining system is created [157]. A virtual machining technology for adjusting feed rate in milling operations is created in order to improve the productivity of part manufacture [158]. Feed rate, depth and width of cut and cutting speed are optimized using the developed method in the study to maximize the rate of material removal in machining operations. The algorithm as well as fundamental of the virtual machining systems in the three axis CNC machining operations as well as five axis CNC machining operations are similar as they are explained in this section. To analyze the accuracy of different method of tool deflection errors in virtual environments, applications of virtual machining system is developed[58]. To produce actual machined components in virtual settings, dimensions and geometrical, errors in three-axis CNC milling machines are considered and simulated in virtual machining system[59]. A virtual machining technology by considering the dimensions and geometrical inaccuracies of a three axis CNC milling machine is introduced in order to produce real machined components in virtual settings [60]. To monitor and minimize the tool deflection error of three axis CNC milling machines, virtual machining technology is proposed [61]. Overall, virtual machining systems can be used in order to simulate and optimize the cutting tool paths, reduce errors, and improve the quality of the final product during 5-axis CNC machining operations.

9- Accuracy analysis and enhancement of rotary axis in 5-axis CNC machine tools

The rotary axis is a critical component of 5-axis CNC milling machines, and its accuracy is essential for achieving precise and high-quality results. Here are some methods to analyze and enhance the accuracy of the rotary axis in 5-axis CNC milling:

1. **Calibration and Compensation:** Calibration and error correction are two of the most efficient ways to increase rotary axis precision. Calibration involves measuring the actual position of the rotary axis and comparing it to the desired position. Any discrepancies can be corrected by compensating for the errors.
2. **Mechanical Design and Stability:** Another important factor in the rotary axis accuracy of mechanical design and stability of the machine. Any excessive vibration or instability can cause inaccuracies in the positioning of the rotary axis. A sturdy and robust machine design can help minimize such vibrations and improve the accuracy.
3. **Lubrication and Maintenance:** Proper lubrication and maintenance of the rotary axis components can also help improve its accuracy. Regular cleaning, lubrication, and replacement of worn parts can prevent any build-up of debris, which can cause inaccuracies and damage to the machine.
4. **Software Optimization:** The CNC software used to control the machine can also play a significant role in the accuracy of the rotary axis. Advanced software algorithms can help compensate for any machine or tool errors, resulting in more precise and accurate milling.
5. **Cutting Tool Selection:** The selection of cutting tools can also impact the accuracy of the rotary axis. Choosing high-quality tools that are appropriate for the materials being machined can help minimize any tool deflection or other errors that can affect the accuracy of the rotary axis.

To analyze and enhance accuracy in rotary axis of 5-axis CNC machine tools, double ballbar testing methods for the servo mismatched errors is implemented [159]. Error modelling and measuring for the rotary table of five-axis machine tools is proposed to calibrate the rotary table of five axis machines [160]. To enhance accuracy of rotary axis, advanced method of on-machine measurement utilizing a touch-trigger probe is proposed [161]. Errors measurement and correction for axial and angular errors in rotating table of a five-axis machine tool is studied to boost performance of the five axis CNC machine tools in the process of component manufacturing [162]. An advanced method of error movements of rotary axes on a five-axis machining center is studied in order to measure and decrease errors of produced parts using 5-axis CNC machine tools [163]. Work-holding rotary axes in five-axis CNC machine tools is studied in order to increase accuracy in process of part production using 5-axis CNC machine tools [164].

In order to depict potential error patterns in the study, cycling error movements of rotary axes for work-holding is studied. Ballbar circle tests are performed for all potential configurations of a five-axis machine tool's linear and rotary axes in order to increase the accuracy of milling processes in the advanced ballbar dynamic tests [165]. Identification of workpiece location on rotary tables in five-axis machining operations is studied to minimize tracking errors and increase accuracy of machined parts [166]. In this study, to minimize the forces transmitted to the rotary drives as torque disturbances, the optimal location of the part on the table is identified and presented. To improve the accuracy of the rotary axis in 5-Axis CNC end milling, geometrical errors correction and uncertainty analysis of the rotary axis in 5-axis ultra-precision machining operation is proposed [167]. Geometrical error modeling, detection, and correction based on linear motion matrix are proposed to improve the accuracy of the rotary axis in five-axis milling machines [168]. To analyze and enhance accuracy in rotary axis of five-axis CNC machine tools, detection and adjustment of geometrical inaccuracies of rotary axes of five-axis machines is proposed [169].

In conclusion, the accuracy of the rotary axis in 5-axis CNC milling can be enhanced by calibrating and compensating for any errors, designing and maintaining a stable mechanical system, optimizing the software, and selecting appropriate cutting tools. A combination of these methods can help achieve precise and high-quality results.

10- Machining operations of flexible thin-walled parts

Machining flexible thin-walled parts in 5-axis CNC milling can be challenging due to the part's delicate nature. However, with proper techniques and tool selection, it is possible to achieve high precision and accuracy. Here are some machining operations that can be used for flexible thin-walled parts in 5-axis CNC milling:

1. Clamping: The part needs to be clamped properly to avoid any movement during machining. Clamping must be done gently and using a soft material such as rubber or foam to avoid any deformation of the part.
2. Tool selection: It is essential to select the right tool for machining thin-walled parts. For instance, a ball-end mill with a small diameter can be used to minimize the cutting forces and prevent the tool from penetrating the part.
3. Milling strategy: Machining thin-walled parts can cause vibration, which can lead to a poor surface finish or even damage to the part. Using a trochoidal milling strategy, where the tool path follows a spiral pattern, can help reduce vibration and improve surface finish.
4. Machining sequence: It is recommended to perform roughing operations first, followed by finishing operations. Roughing operations remove the bulk of the material, and finishing operations produce the final surface finish.
5. Toolpath optimization: It is essential to optimize the toolpath to avoid excessive cutting forces and prevent the tool from digging into the part. Using adaptive toolpaths that adjust the feed rate based on the cutting conditions can help optimize the toolpath.
6. Coolant: Using coolant during machining can help dissipate heat and reduce the risk of thermal deformation. A mist coolant system can be used to minimize the amount of coolant and prevent any damage to the part.

A 5-Axis adaptive flank milling operations for flexible thin-walled components is developed to enhance dimensional accuracy of machined parts [170]. On-machine measurement inspection system-based integrated machining deviation compensation strategy is developed in the study to increase accuracy and efficiency in 5-axis flank milling operations of flexible thin-walled parts. In order to decrease the deformation of the workpieces in 5-Axis ball-end milling operations, impact of tool inclination angle on thin-walled components' elastic deformation by using the finite element method is proposed [171].

To compensate the deformation error in five-axis CNC flank milling operations of components with thin walls including blades, a sophisticated cutting tool route optimization technique is presented [29]. An advanced error prediction and compensation strategy in 5 Axis milling operations of flexible thin-wall parts is suggested to improve precision in machined parts [172]. To increase accuracy of machined thin-walled parts using 5-axis CNC machine tools, spiral-Layer machining for making thin-wall structures is studied [173]. In order to study the dynamic behavior of a turbine blade during five-axis milling machine operations, a measurement equipment for empirical modal analysis of thin-walled metal components is constructed [174].

Overall, machining flexible thin-walled parts in 5-axis CNC milling requires careful planning, proper techniques, and attention to detail. With the right approach, it is possible to achieve high precision and accuracy while maintaining the integrity of the part.

11- Tool wear prediction in 5 Axis milling operations

Tool wear prediction in 5-axis milling operations can be a challenging task due to the complexity of the process and the many variables involved. However, there are several approaches that can be taken to predict tool wear in these operations. One approach is to use physical models that simulate the cutting process and predict tool wear based on the calculated cutting forces, temperature, and other relevant parameters. These models can be calibrated using experimental data and can provide accurate predictions of tool wear for a given set of cutting conditions. Another approach is to use machine learning algorithms to predict tool wear based on historical data. This approach requires a large dataset of cutting conditions and corresponding tool wear measurements, which can be used to train the machine learning model. Once the model is trained, it can be used to predict tool wear for new cutting conditions. Furthermore, there are several sensor-based methods for monitoring tool wear in real-time during 5-axis milling operations. These methods use sensors to measure various parameters such as temperature, vibration, and acoustic emission, which can be used to detect changes in the cutting process and predict tool wear.

A comparison of 3- and 5-axis CNC centers for free-form cutting of difficult-to-cut materials is presented in order to evaluate and improve the tool wear condition in machining operations [175]. So, time and cost of part production using CNC machine tools are decreased. Tool wear estimation in micro-machining operations using 5 axis CNC machine tools is investigated in order to enhance cutting tool life in milling operations of free form surfaces [176]. The capacity to estimate tool usage (wear) through using two encoding approaches and backpropagation-type neural networks is assessed in this study, which also examines the link between cutting force parameters and tool usage. To boost productivity in the component manufacturing process utilizing CNC machine tools, a cutting tool-wear and surface roughness diagnostic based on bayesian networks is offered [177]. Neural network-based sensor fusion is proposed to estimate tool wear during CNC milling in order to prolong cutting wear resistance [178]. Pre-Polishing process optimization on a 5-axis milling machine operations is proposed to lower the process cost while keeping particular roughness [179].

Overall, predicting tool wear in 5-axis milling operations requires a combination of physical models, machine learning algorithms, and sensor-based monitoring techniques. By using these approaches, manufacturers can optimize cutting conditions and reduce tool wear, leading to improved efficiency and cost savings. Machine learning techniques such as neural networks and support vector machines can be used to model the relationship between tool wear and process variables such as cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut. This can help to develop more accurate tool wear prediction models. Moreover, multi-scale modeling can be used to simulate the complex interactions between the tool and the workpiece at different length scales. This can provide a more detailed understanding of the mechanisms that contribute to tool wear and help to develop more accurate prediction models.

12- Cutting tool temperatures estimation

The temperature of cutting tools during 5-axis milling operations can be estimated using various techniques, including analytical models, experimental measurements, and simulation methods. Here are some possible approaches:

1. Analytical models: Analytical models use equations and theoretical principles to estimate the cutting tool temperature. These models can be based on heat transfer theory, thermodynamics, and other principles. One example is the finite element method (FEM), which can be used to simulate the temperature distribution of a cutting tool during a milling operation.
2. Experimental measurements: To detect the temperature throughout milling, temperature sensors can be mounted to the cutting tool or the workpiece. For example, thermocouples or infrared cameras can be used to measure the temperature of the cutting tool during machining.
3. Simulation methods: Simulation methods can be used to estimate the temperature of the cutting tool based on a computer model of the machining process. For example, finite element analysis (FEA) can be used to simulate the heat transfer and temperature distribution during milling.

The temperature management and machine dynamics in chip breaking utilizing CNC toolpaths is examined to reduce cutting tool breakage in end milling [180]. To improve the surface properties of machined parts by monitoring cutting tool temperatures throughout milling operations, 5-axis milling of SLM Ti-6Al-4V spherical components is studied [181]. To reduce cutting tool failure during milling operations, an online tool temperature monitoring technique based on physics-guided infrared image characteristics and artificial neural network is studied [182]. To decrease cutting temperature in machining operations, the analytical model-based cutting tool temperature prediction approach for end milling operations utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools is studied [183]. To obtain the optimized cutting process parameters, analytical temperature predictive modeling and non-linear optimization in 5 Axis CNC machining operations is proposed [184]. To obtain the optimum milling condition during Al2024-T3 milling operations, an empirical evaluation of the impact of cutting parameters on workpiece internal temperature is proposed [185]. High bandwidth monitoring in interrupted cutting of challenging materials is examined to reduce cutting tool breakage in dry machining [186].

Overall, the estimation of cutting tool temperatures during 5-axis milling operations requires a combination of theoretical understanding, experimental measurements, and simulation methods. This information can be used to optimize the machining process and improve the efficiency and quality of the final product.

13- Flank milling operations in 5-axis CNC machine tools

Flank milling is a type of milling operation that involves cutting the side or flank of a workpiece using a cutting tool. In a 5-axis CNC machine tool, flank milling can be performed using various cutting strategies and tool paths. It involves cutting the material from the side of the workpiece rather than from the top or bottom. Complex forms and curves that would be challenging to produce using conventional milling processes can be easily created using this approach [170]. In 5-axis CNC machining, the cutting tool can be tilted at various angles to approach the workpiece from different directions. This allows for greater flexibility in the machining process and makes it easier to create complex shapes. Flank milling is often used in conjunction with other milling techniques such as contouring and pocketing to create intricate parts with tight tolerances. When performing flank milling operations, it is important to consider factors such as tool path optimization, tool selection, and cutting parameters [187]. The tool path should be optimized to minimize the number of tool changes and to ensure that the tool stays in contact with the workpiece throughout the operation. The cutting parameters should be set to ensure that the tool does not overheat or wear out prematurely .

A review in 5-axis flank milling is proposed to develop the free from flank milling operations using 5 Axis CNC machine tools [188] . This paper examines a survey on flank milling and offers advice for future considerations in optimizing the tool trajectory for flank milling. Figure 6 illustrates end milling, sweep milling, and flank milling procedures [188].

Fig. 6. End milling, sweep milling, and flank milling procedures [188].

Designed, envelope and constraint surfaces are defined in the flank milling operations to determine the best tool path for producing the part. As seen in picture 7, "constraint surfaces" are additional surfaces that hinder the tool trajectory from reaching the "planned surface." [188].

Fig. 7. Designed, envelope and constraint surfaces [188].

Geometrical aberrations in 5-axis elevated flank machining against smoothness is presented to minimize energy during cutting tool paths lead to provide minimal machining time [189]. Computed tool paths for an Impeller surface is presented in the figure 8 [189].

Fig. 8. Computed toolpaths (Impeller surface) [189].

Tool path planning employing CNC normal approximation for 5-axis flank milling of ruled surfaces is investigated to minimize the tool paths errors using optimization methods [190]. Ant colony system techniques for effective tool trajectory tracking for 5-axis flank milling of controlled surfaces is investigated to enhance precision and efficiency to manufacture a component utilizing CNC machine tools [191]. To enhance accuracy in multi-pass five-axis flank milling operations, geometrical errors are measured and compensated [192].

Overall, flank milling in 5-axis CNC machine tools can be a powerful tool for machining complex geometries and producing high-quality parts with tight tolerances. However, it requires careful planning and execution to achieve the desired results. Various optimization techniques such as genetic algorithms and artificial neural networks can be used to determine the optimal cutting parameters for flank milling operations on 5-axis CNC machine tools. This could result in significant improvements in productivity and surface quality.

14- Sweep milling in 5-axis milling operations

Sweep milling is a machining technique that involves cutting a surface by moving the cutting tool in a sweeping motion along a curved or contoured path. In 5-axis milling operations, sweep milling is often used to machine complex surfaces or parts that require a high degree of precision and accuracy. In sweep milling, the tool follows a path that is defined by a series of curves or contours [193]. The tool is typically oriented at a fixed angle to the workpiece surface, and the cutting edge of the tool is moved along the path in a sweeping motion. This allows the tool to remove material from the workpiece in a continuous manner, resulting in a smooth surface finish and reduced machining time [188]. In 5-axis milling operations, sweep milling is often used in conjunction with other techniques, such as adaptive milling or trochoidal milling, to optimize the machining process. By using these techniques in combination, higher material removal rates, lower tool wear and breakage, and better surface finish quality are all achievable.

To improve precision in the machined surfaces, a geometric deviation assessment using the tool swept envelope for a five-axis flank milling tool route is provided [194]. To simulate surface topography of machined parts in ball-end CNC milling processes, swept surface-based approach is studied [195]. Algebraic-based swept volumes for any arbitrary free-form oriented tooling is examined to improve precision in machining operations of free form surfaces [196]. Figure 9 displays a few images from a simulation of 5-axis CNC machining performed using a flat-end cutter on the external surface of the skin of the Utah teapot [196].

Fig. 9. Several frames from a simulation of 5-axis CNC machining performed using a flat-end cutter on the outer surface of the Utah teapot's body. A blue accent in (a) indicates the original surface of the body (half). [196].

Producing cutter sweeping envelopes in five-axis milling using sphere families with two parameters is discussed to increase accuracy in machining operations of canal surfaces [197]. In order to increase accuracy in swept surface machining operations, a real-time surface interpolator algorithm is proposed [198]. The sweep plane method for global collision detection involving workpiece geometry modification in five-axis NC machining operations is examined to detect and prevent the collision between workpiece and cutting tool in machining operations [199]. Overall, sweep milling is a versatile and effective technique for 5-axis milling operations, particularly for machining complex surfaces and parts that require a high degree of precision and accuracy. Future research in this area could focus on optimizing the parameters of the sweep milling process, such as the tool path, cutting speed, and feed rate. This could involve the use of advanced simulation and modeling techniques to predict the behavior of the material during the milling process.

15- Gouging error detection and elimination methods

Gouging is a common problem that can occur during 5-axis CNC machining, especially when the machine is working on complex surfaces or tight corners. Gouging can cause damage to the workpiece, decrease the accuracy of the machining, and even cause the tool to break [36]. To detect and eliminate gouging errors in 5-axis CNC machining, here are some methods:

1. Simulation software: One of the most effective ways to detect gouging errors is by using simulation software. This program lets users to construct a computer-generated model of the machining procedure and simulate it in real-time. The software can detect gouging errors and provide solutions to avoid them.
2. Collision detection: CNC machines have a collision detection system that can detect the collision of the tool with the workpiece or machine components. The system can also detect gouging errors, and if it does, it will automatically stop the machining process.
3. Toolpath optimization: Optimizing the toolpath can help to eliminate gouging errors. By adjusting the toolpath, the tool can avoid tight corners or complex surfaces that could cause gouging.
4. Toolpath verification: Verifying the toolpath can help to detect gouging errors before the machining process begins. The verification process checks the toolpath for any potential gouging errors and provides solutions to eliminate them.

5. Machine calibration: Ensuring that the CNC machine is calibrated properly can also help to eliminate gouging errors. If the machine is not calibrated correctly, it may cause the tool to gouge the workpiece.

To provide gouge detection and gouge-free machining in 5-axis CNC milling operations, a method for detecting and removing 3D curvature gouges detection system is proposed [200]. Sculptured surfaces are machined using five axes CNC machine tools. To avoid gouging error in the 5 axis CNC machine tools operations of sculptured surfaces, localized interference detecting and preventing system can be applied. As a result, surface quality can be improved by using the developed cutting tool paths modification [201]. To detect and eliminate gouge errors in five-axis CNC machining operations of sculptured surfaces, a technique for detecting and preventing interference local gouge is developed [201]. To improve precision of machined sculptured surfaces using 5-axis CNC machine tools, a local gouging error detection and elimination system is proposed [202]. Gouge-free voxel-based machining tool routes in parallel with regard to operation duration and cutting surface outcomes using surface data and generalized cutting geometries are modified to increase the production's component quality employing 5-Axis CNC machine tools [203]. To increase accuracy and safety in five-axis CNC machine tool procedures, the application of penetration-elimination approach in five-axis CNC machining of sculptured surfaces is introduced [204]. Figure 10 depicts the simulation findings, which demonstrate a gouge-free machining process utilizing the technology created for the research [204].

Fig. 10. The simulation's findings to a gouge-free machining procedure [204].

To avoid the gouging error, five-axis machining tool path planning using the principal axis method is developed [205]. Overall, gouging errors can be a significant problem in 5-axis CNC machining, but there are several methods to detect and eliminate them. By using simulation software, collision detection systems, optimizing the toolpath, verifying the toolpath, and ensuring the machine is calibrated properly, gouging errors can be minimized or eliminated. Machine learning algorithms, such as deep learning and reinforcement learning, have shown significant promise in improving error detection and correction. Future research can explore the potential of these techniques for enhancing gouge error detection and correction performance in various domains.

16- Collision detection systems in 5-axis CNC machining operations

Collision detection systems in 5-axis CNC (Computer Numerical Control) machining are designed to prevent the cutting tool or the part from colliding with the machine or other objects during the machining process. This is particularly important in 5-axis machining, where the cutting tool can move in multiple directions simultaneously.

There are several types of collision detection systems used in 5-axis CNC machining. One type is based on the use of sensors, such as limit switches or proximity sensors, which are installed on the machine tool and detect when the tool or part is getting too close to the machine or other objects.

Another type of collision detection system uses software to simulate the machining process and identify potential collisions before they occur. This type of system is often integrated into the CNC control software and can detect collisions based on the machine geometry, tool path, and part geometry. Software-based collision detection systems, use computer algorithms to predict and prevent collisions. These systems typically require a virtual model of the part being machined, as well as information about the machine's capabilities and limitations. The software continuously monitors the movement of the machine and compares it to the virtual model, predicting any potential collisions and adjusting the machine's movement accordingly.

Hardware-based collision detection systems typically use sensors or switches that are placed in strategic locations on the machine. When the machine comes in contact with an object, the sensor or switch is triggered, and the machine stops moving. These systems are generally reliable but may not be able to detect collisions that occur at high speeds. In addition to collision detection, some CNC machines also have automatic tool changers, which can change tools automatically during the machining process. These systems typically use sensors to detect when the current tool is nearing the end of its lifespan and needs to be changed.

One of the challenges of implementing collision detection in 5-axis CNC machining is the complexity of the movements involved. 5-axis machines can move in multiple directions simultaneously, which makes collision detection more difficult than in simpler 3-axis machines. However, advances in technology have made it possible to implement reliable collision detection systems in 5-axis CNC machines.

The workpiece topological updating for five-axis NC machining using the sweep plane approach for global collision detection is addressed to obtain and prevent collisions between workpiece and cutter as well as the collisions between the other parts of the 5 Axis CNC machine tools [199]. To increase safety in machining processes of part production using 5 Axis CNC machine tools, collision detection between the toolholder, workpiece and workpiece fixture can be detected using a developed 3D geometric model of the tool swept volume is modified [206]. Tool-paths for 5-axis ball-ends using globally ensured collision-free orientations are automatically generated to modify and optimize the machining paths along free form surfaces [207]. The modified cutting tool-paths for a model of a bladed disk is shown in the figure 11 [207].

Fig. 11. Tool-path for a bladed disk model encircled by a CC curve (in green with a blue orientation offset curve). Although picture (a) provides a general perspective, image (b) provides a more in-depth look at the tool-path surrounding a single blade. [207].

To detect and rectify collisions based on the largest collision boxes in five-axis CNC machining processes, a collision detection methodology based on the bounded volume and the sweeping plane approach is developed [208]. Overall, collision detection systems are essential in 5-axis CNC machining to guarantee the safety of the machining operation, efficient, and produces high-quality parts. By preventing collisions, these systems can reduce the risk of damage to the machine, the part, and the cutting tool, which can ultimately save time and money. Real-time simulation can be used to predict potential collisions before they occur, allowing the machine to adjust its trajectory and avoid a crash. Researchers could explore the use of real-time simulation in combination with collision detection systems to improve overall machining accuracy and efficiency.

17- Development of post-processor in 5-axis CNC machine tools

A post-processor is an essential component of Computer Numerical Control (CNC) machines. It is responsible for converting a CAM (Computer-Aided Manufacturing) program's toolpath into a language that the CNC machine can understand and execute [209]. A 5-axis CNC machine is a versatile machine tool that can perform a wide range of cutting and machining operations with high precision and accuracy. Developing a post-processor for a 5-axis CNC machine requires careful consideration of several factors.

The processes for creating a post-processor for a 5-axis CNC machine are as follows:

1. Understand the machine's kinematics: The first step in developing a post-processor for a 5-axis CNC machine is to understand the machine's kinematics. This includes the machine's axes of motion, the type of tool head, and the workpiece's orientation.
2. Select a CAM software: Select a CAM software that supports 5-axis machining and is compatible with your CNC machine.
3. Create a tool library: Create a tool library that includes all the tools you will be using on your CNC machine. Each tool should have its unique identifier, cutting parameters, and other relevant information.
4. Define the machining operations: Define the machining operations you want to perform on the workpiece, such as roughing, finishing, drilling, and so on.
5. Generate toolpaths: Generate toolpaths for each machining operation using the CAM software.
6. Create a post-processor file: Create a post-processor file that converts the toolpaths generated by the CAM software into a language that the CNC machine can understand. This file should include information on the machine's kinematics, the tool library, and the machining operations.
7. Test the post-processor: Test the post-processor by running a sample program on the CNC machine. Verify that the machine executes the program correctly and produces the desired results.
8. Refine the post-processor: Refine the post-processor as needed to improve its performance and compatibility with the CNC machine.

An automated post-processor including geometric error correction for 5-axis machine tools is introduced to reduce volumetric inaccuracies in manufactured products brought on by geometric errors [105]. So, the presented post-processor in the study can increase accuracy of machined parts. To make machined components more precise using the 5-axis CNC machine tools, on the basis of the generalized kinematics model of machine tools, a generic five-axis postprocessor is created [102]. To improve processing quality and reduce the total machining time and cost, a five-axis machine tool's post-processor development with optimization tool radius compensation is created [210]. A

postprocessor based on the kinematics model for general five-axis machine tools is developed in order to make machined components more precise using 5-Axis CNC machine tools [211]. An investigation into the creation of a post processor for angle head spindle five-axis machining is presented to improve precision of machined parts with complex shapes [212]. To increase accuracy of curved surfaces in five-axis CNC machining operations, a feedrate scheduling algorithm is presented in order to constrain tool tip position and tool orientation errors under cutting load disturbances [21]. To enhance precision in milling operations of free form surfaces, postprocessor algorithm and feedrate optimization in 5-Axis milling operations is discussed [213].

In summary, developing a post-processor for a 5-axis CNC machine involves understanding the machine's kinematics, selecting a compatible CAM software, creating a tool library, defining machining operations, generating toolpaths, creating a post-processor file, testing the post-processor, and refining it as needed. It is a complex process that requires careful attention to detail and expertise in CNC programming and machining. Post-processing software can be developed to provide real-time feedback to operators during machining operations. This process can involve monitoring the tool condition, detecting potential issues with the machine or the part, and providing suggestions for adjustments to the machining process.

18- Intelligent Computer Aided Process Planning (CAPP) systems

Intelligent Computer Aided Process Planning (CAPP) systems for 5-axis CNC machine tools refer to computer-based software applications that help manufacturing companies plan and design machining processes for complex parts that are to be produced on 5-axis CNC machines. These systems use advanced algorithms and techniques, such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), to generate optimal machining strategies for the given part geometry, material, and production constraints [214]. They can take into account various factors, such as cutting tool selection, tool path generation, cutting parameters, and fixture design, to create a comprehensive plan for the manufacturing process. One of the key advantages of CAPP systems is that they can significantly reduce the time and cost involved in process planning, as well as minimize the risk of errors and defects during machining [215]. They can also improve the efficiency and accuracy of the machining process, leading to higher quality parts and increased productivity.

Some of the specific features that may be included in CAPP systems for 5-axis CNC machine tools include:

- Automated tool selection based on part geometry and material properties
- Generation of optimized tool paths for efficient and accurate machining
- Analysis of cutting forces, tool wear, and other factors to optimize cutting parameters
- Simulation of the machining process to detect potential errors and collisions
- Automatic generation of fixture designs for secure part holding during machining
- Integration with other software tools, such as CAD/CAM systems and enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems.

In terms of improving knowledge management and decision-making in the component manufacturing process, 5-axis CNC tapping machine process planning assisted by smart technology is proposed [39]. To present a reliable decision making system in process of part manufacturing, machining process sequencing and machine assignment in generative feature-based CAPP for 5 –Axis CNC mill-turn machining operations is developed [216]. An advanced CAPP system for 5-axis milling of sculptured surfaces is discussed to improve surface quality when performing machining operations [217]. For micromachining procedures utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools, an automated feature extraction and CNC code creation in a CAPP system is created [218]. To increase efficiency in machining operations, The intelligent system architecture for CNC machine tool processing is presented [219]. Regarding to step-NC machining characteristics, smart cutting tool choosing for milling is presented [220]. Also, process

parameter modification for CAPP applications using micro end milling is explored to present an advanced computer aided process planning [221]. Intelligent feature-based process planning for 5 axis mill-turn components is examined to improve the quality of parts produced via machining processes [222].

Overall, CAPP systems for 5-axis CNC machine tools can offer significant benefits for manufacturing companies looking to improve their machining processes and reduce costs. However, these systems require careful planning and implementation to ensure they are properly integrated into the production workflow and aligned with the company's strategic goals.

19- Advanced machining strategies for smooth cutting tool paths

Machining strategies for smooth cutting tool paths are critical for improving the quality and efficiency of machining operations. There are several advanced machining strategies that can be used to generate smooth cutting tool paths for 5-axis CNC machine tools. Here are a few of them:

1. **Continuous 5-axis machining:** This technique uses the machine's full range of motion to produce a smooth tool path. The cutting tool is kept in contact with the material at all times, which reduces tool chatter and improves surface finish.
2. **Trochoidal milling:** This strategy involves using a series of circular tool paths that overlap slightly to remove material in a smooth, efficient manner. This approach helps to minimize tool wear and extend tool life.
3. **High-speed machining:** This technique involves using high spindle speeds and fast cutting feeds to remove material quickly and efficiently. By reducing cutting forces, it can also help to minimize tool chatter and improve surface finish.
4. **Adaptive machining:** Adaptive machining is a technique that involves adjusting the cutting tool's path and speed in real-time based on the changing material properties and machine dynamics. This technique ensures that the tool always cuts the material in the most efficient and effective way possible, resulting in smooth cutting tool paths and high-quality surface finishes.
5. **Rest machining:** This approach involves removing material only where necessary, leaving the remaining material to support the part during machining. This can help to reduce forces and enhance surface finish by minimizing the volume of material to be machined.
6. **Tool Center Point (TCP) Control:** TCP control is a technique that involves adjusting the machine's tool path based on the tool's center point rather than the tool's tip. This technique ensures that the tool maintains a consistent distance from the workpiece, resulting in smoother cutting tool paths and higher surface finishes.

By employing these advanced machining strategies, 5-axis CNC machine tool operators can achieve smooth cutting tool paths and high-quality surface finishes, improving the overall efficiency and accuracy of the machining process.

To enhance the machining products' surface properties, a smooth tool path generating system for 5-axis machining operations is introduced [223]. In order to considerably enhance 5-axis machining of the nonzero genus mesh surface, a new technique for creating spiral or contour-parallel tool paths is suggested in the study. To improve machining parameters in terms of machine tool motion, stability and cutting forces for 5-axis machining operations, machining process simulation to integrate cutting tool axis selection for 5-axis tool path generation is presented [224].

To precisely forecast the cutting forces when milling free-form objects in five axes machining operations, mechanistic modeling of five-axis machining with a general end mill considering cutter runout is developed [225]. As a consequence, utilizing the study's created approach, the surface quality of machined components is enhanced. In order to provide collision-free, wide-machining-width flank milling pathways with fluid axes motions, an advanced method of generating cutting tool paths for five-axis machining of blisks using barrel cutters is proposed [226].

Enhancing five-axis plunge milling cutter life and cutting effectiveness through modeling and tool path regeneration is presented [227]. So, new cutting tool paths can increase cutter life to improve efficiency in process of part production. To enhance precision and efficiency to produce a component by employing five-axis CNC machine tools, an average surface interpolator approach is developed [198]. Precise 5-axis tool-path approximation in real time with local corner reduction is investigated in order to decrease the tool-tip and the tool-orientation errors in milling operations of free form surfaces [228]. The investigation of real-time local filtering for five-axis linear toolpath under smoothing error restrictions is proposed to provide tighter tolerance in the smoothing error control during milling operations of free form surfaces [229]. There is a lot of potential for using optimization algorithms to generate smooth cutting tool paths that minimize machining time, improve surface finish, and reduce tool wear. These algorithms could be based on machine learning techniques, genetic algorithms, or other optimization methods.

20- Cutting tool paths Optimization for minimum energy consumption

Optimizing cutting tool paths for minimum energy consumption in 5-axis CNC machines involves several factors, such as the type of material being machined, the cutting tool's geometry, the spindle speed, the feed rate, and the cutting depth [230]. Here are some approaches that can be used to optimize cutting tool paths for minimum energy consumption:

1. **Reduce cutting forces:** Cutting forces can be reduced by using a higher helix angle on the cutting tool and minimizing the cutting depth. This will reduce the amount of energy required to overcome the cutting forces and result in lower energy consumption.
2. **Optimize toolpath:** Optimizing the toolpath can also reduce energy consumption. For example, reducing the number of sharp turns or angles in the toolpath can reduce the amount of acceleration and deceleration required, which can result in significant energy savings.
3. **Determine the optimal spindle speed:** The spindle speed should be optimized to ensure that the cutting tool is operating at an optimal speed that balances tool wear and energy consumption. Too high of a speed can cause excess wear on the tool, while too low of a speed can result in longer machining times and increased energy consumption. Reducing the spindle speed can also reduce energy consumption. However, this should be done carefully to ensure that the cutting tool's performance is not compromised.
4. **Use high-efficiency cutting tools:** Choosing high-efficiency cutting tools can also reduce energy consumption. For example, using a carbide tool instead of a high-speed steel tool can significantly reduce the energy required to machine the material.
5. **Optimize coolant usage:** The use of coolant can also affect energy consumption. Using the right amount of coolant can reduce friction and cutting forces, resulting in lower energy consumption.
6. **Minimize the number of tool changes:** Reducing the number of tool changes can help reduce the overall energy consumption of the machining process. This can be achieved by selecting a tool that can perform multiple operations or by optimizing the tool path to minimize the number of tool changes required.
7. **Control cutting parameters:** Cutting parameters such as depth of cut, feed rate and cutting speed should be optimized to reduce energy consumption while maintaining high-quality machining results. This can be achieved through careful analysis of the material being machined and the cutting tool being used.

As a result, cutting tool paths can be optimized for minimum energy consumption in 5-axis CNC, which can lead to reduced energy costs, increased productivity, and improved machining quality. The Cutter orientation improvement for multi-axis NC machining is examined in order to reduce motion axes' power consumption [231]. The machine-based energy-saving tool path generating system is created to reduce the energy consumption in five-axis end milling operations of freeform surfaces [232]. The study presents energy-saving tool path creation to reduce the overall energy consumption in five-axis end milling of freeform surfaces in big items like blades and dies. To achieve the

lowest energy consumption possible during milling processes, energy usage modeling and improvement for feature-based machining is developed [233]. A multi-objective tool path optimization method for free-form surface milling is proposed in order to enhance productivity, energy efficiency, and minimize carbon emissions in part production process [234]. To reduce on total energy usage in machining operations, an energy-saving strategy for rough milling tool path planning system is proposed [235]. To increase the accuracy of produced parts with specified machining accuracy by developing the machining error estimation model, calculation of energy-efficient cutting settings for NC machining processes is presented [236].

Overall, optimizing cutting tool paths for minimum energy consumption in 5-axis CNC machines involves a careful consideration of several factors. By implementing some or all of these approaches, it is possible to significantly reduce energy consumption and improve machining efficiency [237]. Developing real-time optimization algorithms that can adjust cutting parameters during machining operations which can improve energy efficiency and reduce waste.

Recent developments of 5-axis CNC milling machine tool operations is presented in the Table 1.

Topic of research work	References	Finding/ Discoveries
Geometric error modelling and compensation	[98]	A Compensation methodology for systematic errors in 5-axis CNC machine tools is proposed. In comparison to previous compensation techniques, the current compensation approach is basic, uncomplicated, and lacks a singularity point in the model.
	[99]	The volumetric error due to geometric error in the 5 Axis machining operations are calculated. New ways to directly measure the total volumetric error provide less measurement in the error measuring process.
	[104]	5-axis CNC machine tools' structural flaws are precisely diagnosed and corrected for. In order to drastically lower the volumetric error during error compensation, more precise estimations of the error parameters are added.
Errors metrology systems in 5-Axis CNC machine tool	[109]	The examination of five-axis industrial machinery's dynamic correctness using S trajectory deviation is discussed. Without the need for additional workpieces or testing instruments, the recommended non-cutting kinematic test approach may accurately reflect the dynamic accuracy of five axis machine tools. A CNC vertical machining center's positioning, circularity, and static errors are measured. In order to make amends, the repercussions of the various faults on the final section are explored.
	[111]	The examination of five-axis industrial machinery's dynamic correctness using S trajectory deviation is discussed. Without the need for additional workpieces or testing instruments, the recommended non-cutting kinematic test approach may accurately reflect the dynamic accuracy of five axis machine tools. A CNC vertical machining center's positioning, circularity, and static errors are measured. In order to make amends, the repercussions of the various faults on the final section are explored.

	[113]	The investigation of systematic geometric error correction in five-axis machine tools is presented. The proposed technique depends on an error table that assesses the function of each axis using a cubic spline approach and synthetic machine tool simulation.
Machining operations of sculptured surfaces	[116]	During milling sculptured surfaces using 5-axis CNC machine tools, material removal is calculated using models of cutting geometry and forces. Continuous geometric representations of the tool and workpiece are offered in order to pinpoint the region where the cutter and workpiece will make contact for a certain tool path.
	[120]	The optimal cutting positions for 5-axis sculptured surface machining procedures are chosen using Dupin indicators of cutter surface and intended surface. By determining the ideal cutting locations locally for sculptured surface machining, the unique methodologies discussed can completely overcome the drawbacks of conventional approaches like "cutting profiles" and "effective cutting form."
	[123]	It is described how to best place a multi-point, 5-axis tool for complicated sculptured surfaces using a unique convex hull technique. The established methodology's suitability, adaptability, and robustness are demonstrated by producing more accurate and computationally efficient results when compared to other commercial software algorithms.
Feed rate scheduling and optimization systems	[124]	The development of feed optimization for five-axis CNC machines with drive restrictions. Enhanced productivity and linear performance of the five drives are two advantages of the system.
	[126]	For precision five-axis CNC machining, a dynamic feedrate scheduling technique leveraging a dual NURBS curve interpolator is shown. Geometric precision and improved five-axis flank machining performance are benefits of the technique.
	[130]	Process mapping and toolpath adjustment for five-axis ball-end milling are presented in terms of tool motion. The benefits of the technology include reducing machining time while preventing process errors.
Cutting forces prediction and analysis	[141]	It is discussed how to calculate chip volume and cutting force for producing free-form surfaces using flat-end mills. To obtain the highest permitted feed-rate and depth of cut, calculations for the optimal tool orientation generation and the instantaneous cutting chip volume and forces are provided in detail.
	[142]	In 5-axis CNC micro-milling employing flat-end, the numerical modeling of chip plowing volume and forces is studied. High feed rate to reduce ploughing effect are system's advantages.

	[145]	Offline force control and feedrate management for difficult free form surfaces in 5-axis milling are investigated. The benefit of the technology is that it may reduce cycling time while increasing production.
Toolpath and cutter orientation optimization systems	[150]	It is suggested to use the configuration-space search approach to optimize tool orientations for 5-axis machining. The benefit of the system is its ability to automatically design and program tool paths for exceptional productivity 5-axis sculptured surface milling.
	[152]	It is suggested that a surface-based method be used to optimize 5-axis high-speed machining. The benefit of the system is that it can save machining time by using improved cutting tool routes.
	[154]	Through the development of revolution-surface fitting envelopes, effective 5-axis flank CNC machining of free-form surfaces is achieved. The benefit of the system is optimized framework, which enhances both the toolpaths and machining productivity.
	[157]	A virtual machining system is created to study and improve machine tool components using finite element models. The study creates a machine tool model that is entirely digital.
Virtual machining systems	[59]	A virtual machining system is created to produce real machined components in virtual settings. To examine and modify the virtual machined components, errors of real machined parts are recreated and applied.
	[58]	To assess the accuracy of tool deflection error modeling in milled surface prediction, a virtual machining application has been built. In order to reduce them, tool deflection errors of machined components are modelled and applied to the virtual machined parts.
	[160]	It is described how to model and measure errors for rotary tables on five-axis machine tools. The system's advantage is its ability to calibrate and enhance accuracy on the revolving table.
Accuracy analysis and enhancement of rotary axis	[163]	On a five-axis machining center, an effective and automated method is created to calibrate rotary axes' error movements using the R-test. The benefit of the system is that it can detect location mistakes, position-dependent geometric flaws, and finally error maps of rotating axes.
	[166]	The ideal placement of the item on the table is determined in order to reduce the forces applied to the rotary drives as torque disturbances. The study's suggested technique can greatly minimize tracking and contouring inaccuracies.
	[170]	It is recommended to mill flexible thin-walled components using a 5-Axis adaptive flank system based on on-machine monitoring. An iterative toolpath compensation method is developed by altering the
Machining operations of flexible thin-walled parts		

		toolpath in order to minimize machining mistakes and avoid unwanted interference.
	[171]	The finite element approach is used to analyze how tool inclination angle affects the deformations of thin-walled items. The impact of the tool inclination angle is investigated in order to select an optimal tool orientation for the milling of thin-walled components.
	[172]	An advanced error prediction and compensation strategy in 5 Axis milling operations of flexible thin-wall parts is introduced. In milling flexible thin-wall components, great precision is attained using the suggested flexible simulation.
Tool wear prediction in 5 Axis milling operations	[175]	To evaluate and alter the tool wear condition in milling operations, a comparison of 3- and 5-axis CNC centers for free-form machining of difficult materials is presented. The machining time is decreased by more than 17% when using the technology developed for the research.
	[177]	The diagnosis of surface quality and cutting tool wearing using Bayesian networks is provided. In the study, a reliability of 89.5 percent for the prediction of surface roughness and a reliability of 97.3 percent for the diagnostic of cutting tool wear are attained.
	[179]	On a 5-axis milling machine, pre-polishing parameter optimization is demonstrated. The system's advantages include increased processing quality and decreased overall cost and time of machining.
Cutting tool temperatures estimation	[181]	Investigated is 5-axis machining of SLM Ti-6Al-4V spherical components to improve the surface attributes of machined products. The system's advantage is its capacity to regulate how cutting parameters, heat treatment, and surface quality impact each other depending on the kinematics of cutting and tool geometries.
	[183]	For end milling operations employing 5 axis CNC machine tools, a methodology for predicting cutting tool temperature using an analytical method is examined. The physical cutting trials and the suggested approach for predicting cutting tool temperature show excellent agreement.
	[186]	The investigation focuses on high bandwidth temperature monitoring during interrupted cutting of challenging materials. This technique is the first to make it possible to map the temperature variations on the tool geographically, which may be crucial for pinpointing the causes of tool failure.
Flank milling operations in 5 Axis CNC machine tools	[188]	A review in 5-axis flank milling is presented to develop the free from flank milling operations using 5 Axis CNC machine tools. A study of flank milling and advice for future problems with the optimization of the tool trajectory for flank milling is introduced.

	[190]	The optimal tool path for 5-axis flank cutting of ruled surfaces with CNC linear interpolation is being investigated. The system's benefits include improving processing quality while reducing total machining costs and time.
	[192]	Regarding applications to multi-pass flank milling in 5 axis CNC machining processes, geometric criteria for tangent continuity of swept tool envelope are examined. To improve precision in the machined components, the tool path and tool shape are used to manage the tool envelope surface.
Sweep milling in 5 Axis milling operations	[194]	A five-axis flank milling cutter path examination for geometric deviations using the tool swept environment is proposed to increase the accuracy of the machined surfaces
	[196]	Accurate algebraic-based swept dimensions for any free-form tool shape are defined in order to verify multi-axis CNC machining. Increasing the accuracy of machined items is one of the technology's advantages.
	[198]	For precise CNC machining of sweeps, a real-time surface interpolator technology is presented. The system's benefits include improved machining precision and reliability.
Gouging error detection and elimination methods	[202]	In five-axis sculptured surface machining processes utilizing flat-end tools, a method for local gouging error identification and removal is created. Optimized cutting tool paths with the gouging error detection can increase the precision of machined parts.
	[203]	Using surface data and generalized cutting geometry, gouge-free voxel-based machining tool paths are simultaneously generated. So, the accuracy of machined parts are improved.
	[205]	Tool path planning for five-axis machining utilizing the primary axis approach is created in order to prevent the gouging errors. The system's advantages include increased processing quality and decreased overall cost and time of machining.
Collision detection systems	[206]	Using a generated 3D geometric model of the tool swept volume, collisions between the toolholder, workpiece, and clamping fixture may be identified. Cutting-edge collision detection systems may be seen to be triggered by undercut and overcut throughout free form milling.
	[207]	It is created to automatically generate 5-axis ball-end toolpaths with globally ensured collision-free orientations. To ensure collision-free orientations in free form machining processes, global optimizations are performed to the tool-path.
	[208]	For five-axis NC machining processes, a novel collision prevention approach and its interaction with collision detection are presented. The work greatly lessens the collision prevention approach's temporal complexities.

Development of post-processor for 5-axis CNC machine tools	[102]	On the basis of an extended mechanics model of a machine tool, a five-axis postprocessor is created. The system's advantages are modified machining routes that improve accuracy and cut down on cutting time.
	[210]	A five-axis machine tool post-processor is created with radius correction for the optimization tool. The system's advantages include increased processing quality and decreased overall cost and time of machining.
	[212]	The creation of a post processor for angle head spindle-based five-axis machining is shown. Increasing accuracy and reliability in the machined parts are the system's advantages.
Intelligent Computer Aided Process Planning (CAPP) systems	[39]	The 5-axis CNC tapping machine's intelligent computer-aided process planning is displayed. Providing a higher intelligent manufacturing platforms within the industry 4.0 concept is the system's advantages.
	[219]	It presents the architecture of an integrated process for programming CNC machine tools. The benefits of the system include its ability to raise the degree of technology of CNC machine tool programming.
	[222]	For 5 axis mill-turn components, sophisticated functionality process planning is examined. The system's advantages include a quick and precise process design, a group code, and related procedures created by the program.
Advanced machining strategies for smooth cutting tool paths	[224]	A simulation of the machining process that incorporates the choice of the cutting tool axis for the creation of 5-axis tool paths is shown. It is possible to preserve safety and fluid machine tool operation while cutting actual machining time by up to 30% by optimizing tool posture along the tool path.
	[226]	Tool path creation is created for the five-axis machining of blisks using barrel cutters. The study's designed solution can be used to avoid collisions between the barrel tool and the blisk.
	[227]	It is discussed how modeling and tool path generation can increase cutting efficiency and prolong cutter life in five-axis plunge milling. To increase cutting tool life throughout machining processes, a better simulation technique is provided.
Optimized cutting tool paths for minimum energy consumption	[232]	The machine-based energy-saving tool path generation system is created to reduce the energy consumption in five-axis end milling operations. More than 25% of the total energy used is saved by the recommended solution, demonstrating its efficacy as a way for reducing overall energy consumption.
	[235]	To reduce overall energy consumption in machining processes, a system for designing rough milling tool paths that is energy-efficient has been devised. The recommended tool path generating procedures in conjunction with the ideal parameters can reduce total

		energy consumption by up to 30% when compared to conventional rough milling cutting settings.
	[236]	To increase the accuracy of produced parts, cutting parameters determination regarding the energy-efficient methods for NC machining operations is presented. The R-test concepts are used to create a mathematical machining error estimate model that selects the best energy-efficient cutting settings.

Table 1. Recent developments of 5-axis CNC milling machine tool operations.

21- Conclusion and future research work directions

5-axis CNC machining is a rapidly evolving technology that has numerous applications in industries such as aerospace, automotive, medical, and others. To generate new concepts for next research projects in the field of study, the most recent advancements in 5-axis CNC machine tool operations are examined and presented in the current research work. Geometric error modelling and compensation are presented to improve precision in machined parts. Errors metrology systems in 5-axis CNC machine tool are developed in order to accurately measure and compensate the errors of machine tools. Machining operations of sculptured surfaces using 5-axis CNC machine tools are analyzed in order to increase to improve manufactured parts' dimensional accuracy and surface integrity. Feed rate scheduling and optimization systems in -axis CNC machine tool operations are developed to make the component production process more efficient. To provide ability of cutting force and cutting tool system along machining paths, cutting forces prediction and analysis are introduced. Toolpath and cutter orientation optimization systems are introduced in order to increase surface quality as well as accuracy in produced parts. Virtual machining systems are created to create and analyze real cutting in virtual worlds. To enhance precision in free form surface milling processes using 5-axis CNC machine tools, rotary axis are analyzed and modified. Machining operations of flexible thin-walled parts using 5-axis CNC machine tools are analyzed in order to increase dimensional accuracy of produced parts. Tool wear prediction in 5 Axis milling operations is presented to analyze and modify performance of cutting tools in milling operations. To decrease cutting tool failure in milling operations, cutting tool temperatures estimation is proposed. Flank and sweep milling operations in 5-axis CNC machine tools is investigated to increase machining abilities of parts with free form surfaces. The gouging error along machining paths of 5-axis CNC machine tools are detected in order to be eliminated. It is possible to increase the safety of machining processes by developing the collision detection systems in 5-axis operations using CNC machine tools. Post processors in 5-axis CNC machine tools are developed in order to compensate the errors as well as optimize cutting tool location throughout machining pathways. To increase quality as well as knowledge management in process of part manufacturing, CAPP systems are developed. Advanced machining strategies for smooth cutting tool paths are developed to increase quality of machined surfaces using 5-axis CNC machine tools. Optimized cutting tool paths for minimum energy consumption are instigated to make the component production process more efficient using minimized energy consumption. To improve the productivity and precision of the component production process utilizing 5 axis CNC machine tools, geometric error modelling and compensation methodologies, advanced errors metrology systems, optimization methodology of cutting tool paths and gouging error detection and elimination methods are developed. To increase cutting tool life as well as surface quality of machined parts, cutting forces, cutting tool temperatures and circumstances of cutting tool wear throughout machining procedures are predicted. Machining operations of sculptured surfaces, sweep milling and Flank milling operations in 5-axis CNC machine tools are studied to increase capabilities of five axis CNC machine tools in machining operations of free form surfaces. Advanced CAPP and collision detection systems are developed in order to improve both production scheduling as well as safety capabilities during 5 Axis CNC machining operations.

To improve the experience of novice operators in milling operations on complicated surfaces using 5-axis CNC machine tools, more advanced virtual environments should be developed for the educational programs. Therefore, by utilizing the created virtual machining systems, the price and duration of correct manufacturing may be reduced. In order to enhance the efficiency and dependability of the component production process, machine tool vibrations as well as the potential for chatter along cutting tool paths can be examined. It is possible to simulate and examine the machine tool parts energy consumption like electric engines, pumps, and moving axes in virtual environments to maximize the added value of part production processes. Additionally, it can be reduced by adopting changed cutting tool paths to improve the productivity of the component production process. When employing 5-axis CNC machine tools, the surface roughness of the generated components may be anticipated, examined, and changed in accordance with the required designing circumstances. Advanced collision detection systems may also be created to improve safety in machining operations according to the requirement for machining operations of complicated parts with free form surfaces like airfoils and impellers utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tools. The optimum machining techniques for producing complex components can be determined by analyzing and modifying the experiences and expertise of machining scientists in the use of 5-axis CNC machine tools. So that an enhanced Computer Aided Process Planning may be presented, customized versions of machining methods can be created (CAPP). Utilizing 5 Axis CNC milling machine equipment, it is possible to acquire optimal toolpath planning with force mechanistic models to increase precision in the flank milling operations. Reducing energy consumption in 5-axis CNC machining is an important area of future research, as it can lead to cost savings and environmental benefits. There are also several potential areas of research for the future of 5-axis CNC milling machine tools, including:

1. Control algorithms: One area of research could be focused on developing more advanced control algorithms for 5-axis CNC milling machines. These algorithms could improve the accuracy and precision of the machines, enabling them to produce more complex and intricate parts.
2. Advanced programming techniques: Researchers could explore the development of more efficient and accurate programming methods for 5-axis machining. This could include the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms to optimize tool paths and reduce machining time. Computer-aided manufacturing (CAM) software is a crucial component in CNC machining, as it converts 3D designs into machine code that can be executed by the CNC machine. Advancements in CAM software could improve the speed and accuracy of 5-axis CNC machining, as well as enable the use of more complex tool paths and strategies.
3. Machine learning and AI for tool path optimization: Another area of research could be the use of machine learning and artificial intelligence to optimize tool paths for 5-axis CNC machining. By analyzing data from previous machining operations, these algorithms could learn to predict the most efficient tool paths for a given part geometry, material, and cutting tool.
4. Adaptive control for tool wear and tool breakage: One limitation of 5-axis CNC machining is the potential for tool wear and tool breakage. Future research could focus on the development of adaptive control systems that can monitor tool wear and adjust cutting parameters in real time to minimize the impact of tool wear and tool breakage on part quality.
5. Material removal rates: Another area of research could be focused on improving material removal rates, which would increase the efficiency of the machines and reduce production time. This could involve developing new tooling, optimizing cutting parameters, or exploring new machining techniques.
6. Automation and robotics: With the rise of Industry 4.0 and the increasing demand for automation in manufacturing, there is also potential for research focused on integrating 5-axis CNC milling machines with robotic systems. This could include developing new software and hardware solutions to enable seamless communication and coordination between the machines and robots.
7. Multi-tasking machines: Another potential area of research could be focused on developing multi-tasking 5-axis CNC milling machines, which would enable manufacturers to perform multiple operations in a single setup. This would reduce production time and increase efficiency.

8. In-process monitoring and control: Real-time monitoring and control of machining processes can improve efficiency and accuracy. Researchers could investigate the use of sensors and other monitoring techniques to optimize 5-axis machining processes.
9. Sustainability: As environmental concerns continue to grow, there may also be a focus on developing more sustainable machining processes for 5-axis CNC milling machines. This could involve exploring new cutting fluids, reducing energy consumption, or optimizing tool life to reduce waste.
10. Utilizing regenerative braking: Regenerative braking is a technique that can be used to recapture energy that would otherwise be lost during deceleration. In a 5-axis CNC machine, this could involve using regenerative braking to capture energy from the movement of the spindle or the axes during deceleration.
11. Implementing efficient cooling systems: Cooling systems are an essential component of any CNC machine, but they can also consume a significant amount of energy. Implementing efficient cooling systems, such as those that use chilled air or liquid, can help to reduce energy consumption.
12. Advancements in machine design: There is potential for research into new machine designs that could further improve the capabilities of 5-axis CNC machining. This could include improvements to the accuracy and speed of the machine, as well as the development of new tools and accessories that enable even more complex machining operations.
13. Exploring alternative machining methods: Finally, researchers could explore alternative machining methods that use less energy than traditional 5-axis CNC machining. For example, additive manufacturing techniques like 3D printing can be used to create complex parts with less waste and energy consumption.
14. Hybrid manufacturing: Finally, future research could explore the integration of 5-axis CNC machining with other manufacturing processes, such as additive manufacturing or electrochemical machining, to enable the production of parts with even greater complexity and precision. This could open up new opportunities in industries such as aerospace, medical devices, and automotive manufacturing.

Overall, the potential for future research in 5-axis CNC machining is vast, and new developments in this field could have significant implications for many industries. These are a few concepts for potential future research projects aimed at improving the manufacturing method utilizing 5-axis CNC machine tool operations.

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